

Socio-Demographic and Clinicopathological Study of Ovarian Cancer in Tertiary Care Hospital of North Central Region of India

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ABSTRACT:

Ovarian cancer has progressively become leading cause of death in females of worldwide and has second position in the most common gynecological malignancy in India. This study was to evaluate the causative factors, clinical and histopathological detail of ovarian cancer cases registering in cancer hospital in Gwalior, and to increase awareness of gynecological malignancy among central region of India. Study was carried out in 56 cases of clinically proven ovarian cancer patients at cancer hospital and research institute, Gwalior, India. Different variables including age of patients at diagnosis, parity of patients, clinical profile includes levels of CA125, histological types and socio-demographic data were collected and analyzed. In this study, 87.5% of the cases were suffering from malignant while only 12.5 % had benign tumor. Most common symptom of complaints is abdominal distension (48.21%), abdominal pain (32.14%) and lower abdominal lump (26.78%). Multiparity was associated with the malignant ovarian cancer in 85.71% patients. This study found the epithelial ovarian cancer as the most common malignancy and both serous (25%) and mucinous cyst adenocarcinoma (21.42%) was the common variant of ovarian carcinoma found in our study.

Keyword: Cancer, Ovarian tumor, epithelial, histopathology, malignancy

INTRODUCTION

Ovarian cancer is the fifth leading cause of death from gynecological malignancy Worldwide [1]. It has emerged as second most common gynecological malignancies affecting Indian women and the third leading cause of death among Indian women trailing behind cervical and breast cancer. Epithelial carcinoma is the most common occurring histotype of ovarian cancer which commonly occurs at the age of the incidence of is 55 to 65 years [2]. The incidence and mortality of ovarian cancer is continuously increasing and despite of extensive medical research, till now its etiology is not fully understood [3]. Various risk factors are associated with ovarian cancers such as family history, nulliparity, smoking, obesity and fertility drugs [4]. Moreover combined oral contraceptive use and estrogen alone hormone replacement therapy for more than 6 months have been documented as the protective factors [5, 6]. Even use of cosmetic talc and some aspect of diet (i.e. Saturated fats, refined carbohydrates) may be associated with the increased risk of ovarian cancer [7].

Ovaries are not only the primary but the favorite site to get metastatic deposits from other abdominal cancer. Anatomical location of the ovaries and the nature of the disease which spread in the form of diffused carcinosis create tumor related abnormality [8]. Depending upon the stage of tumor and pathology, standard treatment includes surgery and chemotherapy [9]. Early detection of the disease has higher survival rate up to 85% but due to unclear symptoms and nonspecific biomarker, survival rate decreased to 30% [10].

In order to analyze the role of effective clinical and non clinical factors in ovarian cancer and its complications, this study was undertaken to report the socio-demographical, clinical and histopathological data of ovarian cancer patients in one of the cancer centre in north central region of India.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

In our single-centre, retrospective study 56 cases of ovarian tumors were examined in the Cancer Hospital and Research Institute. This is a tertiary health care hospital and receives

patients from all over north central region of Madhya Pradesh. These Patients were from Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics admitted in August 2013 to August 2014. Histopathological data was available only for 51 patients. This analysis included age at diagnosis, clinical presentation, bilaterality, multilocularity, operative findings and histopathological analysis. Depending upon the availability of other details of patient, we also looked forward with the non clinical features of patients such as, information about the marital status, age at marriage, religious confession, socio-economic status, occupational status, addiction pattern, and diet pattern, symptoms of complaints and duration of symptoms. The data was analyzed using SPSS (version 2000) software. The data is presented in descriptive statistics in term of percentages and total number of case.

RESULTS

The study was performed in 56 patients having ovarian cancer were examined who was operated in Department of Surgical Oncology. In present study results show that, malignancy was diagnosed in 87.5% (49 cases) while 12.5% (7 cases) had benign tumor (Table 1). Majority of the patients (25%) were in the age group of 38 to 47 years. The oldest patient in our study was a 75 years old lady and the youngest one was 18 years girls. In this study, malignancy was presented with the complaints of abdominal distension, abdominal pain and lump in abdomen in 34.69%, 26.53% and 26.53% of patients respectively as the common symptoms whereas 18 % cases of malignant were found asymptomatic. Most of the cases of benign tumors 13 case (71.42%) were presented with the complaints of abdominal pain. Duration of these complaints of symptoms was greater than one month in most of the malignant (57.14%) as well as in benign cases (71.42%)(Table 2).

We found in this study that most the patients (89.28%) were belonging to rural area. However with regards to the religious confession, we found majority of the patients (91.07%) were Hindus, 7.14% were Muslims and only single patient belonged to Sikh community. Occupational status shows that

most of the patients were belonged to farmer (44.64%) and labor (33.92%) families and only 7.14% patients were addicted for tobacco and rest (92.86%) was addicted for nothing. Data from diet pattern resulted that out of total 56 patients 75% were vegetarian and 25% patients were non vegetarian. Regarding the marital status, 8.92% subjects were unmarried in which 60% girls were associated with malignancy. The age of females at the time of marriage was 16- 20 years in majority of the malignant cases (55.10%) and 10-15 years in 38.77% of the malignant cases. In this study we found that most of the malignant cases (51.02%) were occurred in reproductive age followed by postmenopausal women (48.97%). Benign tumor cases were found majorly (71.4%) in unmarried girls and at reproductive age. Nulliparity was found to be associated with only 14.28% of malignant cases and 28.57% of benign cases. Majority of the malignant patients (85.71%) were parous, 64.28% women of them were having one to three children and 35.72% women were having more than three children (Table 3).

In the study of preclinical features, bilaterality was found with 24.48% of malignant cases and 14.28% of benign

cases. Multilocularity was found to be present only in 30.61% cases of malignant OC. In majority of the malignant cases (46.93%), lesion were complex, in 36.73% cases only cystic lesion was present and 16.32% cases was found with solid lesion whereas in 71.42% of benign cases lesion was cystic. Ascites were found in 48.21% of all ovarian tumor cases in which 66.6% cases were EOC. It was observed that 58.92% patients had raised serum CA125 level (i.e. >35 U mL⁻¹) and 41.07% was found with normal serum CA125 level (i.e. ≤35 U mL⁻¹). (Table 4)

Histopathologically, surface epithelial tumors was present in 66.07% of all ovarian cancer cases, germ cell tumor were found in 8.92% cases and sex-cord stromal cell tumor were present in 7.14% ovarian neoplasm cases. In this study, serous was the most common (23.21%) tumor subtype followed by mucinous (19.64%) tumor. Cystadenoma was the most common histotype in benign ovarian tumor. Most of the patients with serous neoplasm were found in the age group of 40-50 years and patients with mucinous neoplasm were commonly found in age group of 29-39 years (Table 5).

Table 1: Distribution of ovarian cancer patients according to benign and malignant conditions

Type of tumor	Number of patients (N)	Percentage from total ovarian tumors (%)
Benign tumors	7	12.5
Malignant tumors	49	87.5
Total	56	100

Table 2: Distribution of benign and malignant ovarian neoplasm according to different age groups, symptoms and duration of presenting complaints

Patients Characteristics	Benign		Malignant		Percentage from total ovarian tumors (%)
	N	%	N	%	
Age					
18-27	3	42.85	3	6.12	10.71
28-37	2	28.57	11	22.44	23.21
38-47	0	0.00	14	28.57	25.00
48-57	1	14.28	12	24.48	23.21
58-67	1	14.28	7	14.28	14.28
68-75	0	0.00	2	4.08	3.57
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Presenting complaints					
Abdominal distension	1	14.29	12	24.49	23.21
Lump in abdomen	1	14.29	6	12.24	12.50
Abdominal pain	4	57.14	10	20.41	25.00
Constitutional	1	14.29	7	14.29	14.29
Post-menopausal Bleeding	0	0.00	3	6.12	5.36
Discharge/ Secretion	0	0.00	3	6.12	5.36
Asymptomatic	0	0.00	8	16.33	14.29
Abdominal distension	1	14.29	12	24.49	23.21
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Duration of symptoms					
≤ One month	2	28.57	21	42.85	41.07
> One month	5	71.42	28	57.14	58.92
Total	7	100	49	100	100

Table 3: Socio-demographic and reproductive features of ovarian cancer patients and their distribution with relation to benign and malignant tumors

Patients Characteristics	Benign		Malignant		Percentage from total ovarian tumors (%)
	N	%	N	%	
Habitat (Socio-economic status)					
Rural	5	71.43	45	91.84	89.29
Urban	2	28.57	4	8.16	10.71
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Religion					
Hindu	7	100	44	89.80	91.07
Muslim	0	0	4	8.16	7.14
Sikh	0	0	1	2.04	1.79

Total	7	100	49	100	100
Occupational status of family					
Labour	2	28.57	17	34.69	33.93
Farmer	4	57.14	21	42.86	44.64
Professional worker	1	14.29	5	10.20	10.71
Government employee	0	0.00	6	12.24	10.71
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Age at marriage					
Unmarried	2	28.57	3	6.12	8.93
10-15	2	28.57	19	38.78	37.50
16-20	3	42.86	27	55.10	53.57
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Menopausal status					
Yes	2	28.57	24	48.98	46.43
No	5	71.43	25	51.02	53.57
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Parity					
0	2	28.57	7	14.29	16.07
1-3	4	57.14	27	55.10	55.36
>3	1	14.29	15	30.61	28.57
Total	7	100	49	100	100

Table 4: Distribution of benign and malignant ovarian neoplasm according to the preclinical and histological features and tumor marker level of CA125

Patients Characteristics	Benign		Malignant		Percentage from total ovarian tumors (%)
	N	%	N	%	
Bilaterality					
Yes	2	28.57	17	34.69	33.93
No	5	71.43	32	65.31	66.07
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Multilocularity					
Yes	0	0	15	30.61	26.79
No	7	100	34	69.39	73.21
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Lesions					
Cystic	5	71.43	18	36.73	41.07
Solid	1	14.29	8	16.33	16.07
Cystic and solid	1	14.29	23	46.94	42.86
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Ascites					
Yes	2	28.57	25	51.02	48.21
No	5	71.43	24	48.98	51.79
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Tumor marker level of CA-125 (U/ml)					
>35 U/ ml	3	42.86	30	61.22	58.93
<35 U/ ml	4	57.14	19	38.78	41.07
Total	7	100	49	100	100
Histological features					
Surface Epithelial Tumors	6	85.71	35	72.92	74.55
Germ Cell Tumor	1	14.29	7	14.58	14.55
Sexcord stromal cell tumor	0	0	6	12.50	10.91
Total	7	100	48	100	100

Table 5: Classification of ovarian neoplasm on the basis of histopathological subtypes

Histological features	Number of patients (N)	Percentage from total ovarian tumors (%)
Serous	13	23.64
Mucinous	11	20.00
Endometrioid	5	9.09
Cystadenoma	9	16.36
Adenocarcinoma	5	9.09
Yolk sac tumor	1	1.82

Choiocarcinoma	1	1.82
Immature teratoma	1	1.82
Mature cystic teratoma	4	7.27
Small cell carcinoma	2	3.64
Round cell carcinoma	2	3.64
Leiomyosarcoma	1	1.82
Total	55	100

*histopathology Data is summarized from 55 patients

DISCUSSION

In India, ovarian cancer is progressively became third most common cancer after cervical and breast cancer. Despite of available medical techniques including surgery and chemotherapy, death rate is high due to difficulty in early diagnosis. This retrospective study of ovarian cancer patients was carried out in a cancer care centre in the central region of India with an aim to evaluate the clinical, histopathological findings and socio-demographic variables in patients. A total of 56 subjects of histopathologically proved ovarian cancer were included in this analysis. In the present study, 87.5% cases (49 cases) had malignant ovarian cancers in clinical investigation while only 12.5% had benign tumor.

In our study, observed mean age for benign tumor was 35.45 year and 45.52 year for malignant OC. As Patient's age increases the disease complications become worst thus in elderly cases and in postmenopausal women its incidence increases with age and attain a peak. Interestingly, even few cases have been identified in their child hood stage of life. In contrast to adult ovarian cancer where mostly cases belong to epithelial cell origin, about 2/3rd in child stage is due to germ cell tumor [11]. In present study, the age at diagnosis started increasing from 29-39 years and reached a peak value at 40-50 years. Apart from that previous studies reported that the average age of 52.6 years with age range from 33 to 71 years of the subjects having ovarian cancer and 48.0 years of age with range from 16 to 76 years of benign ovarian tumor [12]. Late diagnosis is the key factor behind increasing incident rate of ovarian cancer [13]. As the disease was diagnosed later hence this may lead low life expectancy among the study population of this study.

Ovarian cancer is often called as silent disease as there is no physical sign of diagnosis besides symptoms is often ambiguous. In most of the cases, the patient experience abdominal or GI pain, urinary problems and vaginal symptoms. Moreover pelvic pain is the first symptom in early stage of ovarian cancer [14]. In Present study we found that abdominal distension, pain and lump in abdomen were the common (in 73.4% cases) symptoms for malignant tumor. Majority of similar studies reported abdominal pain, distension and mass as most common symptoms and 10% patients were asymptomatic in malignant cases [15]. It has been observed that infertility and low parity is associated with increased risk of non familial ovarian cancer. Apart from that multiparty and use of oral contraceptives decrease the risk but the exact reason is unclear. Some controversies were also reported in few studies where no correlation of malignancy found with parity while on contrary it has been reported that 19-47% of ovarian tumors case was multiparous [16, 17]. In our study we found that 55.35 % case ovarian cancer woman had 1-3 parity while only 16 % was with no parity but they diagnosed positive for the disease.

Ascites is a main clinical manifestation of malignant tumor. Previous study [18] has been observed that ascites were found in 89% of advanced stage ovarian cancer and 17% in early stage diseases and. In our study, ascites was found in 55.1% of

malignant tumor which was the cause of abdominal pain as more fluid accumulates. Moreover, some benign patient (28.57%) was also showed this clinical symptom.

The incidences of bilaterality have been observed roughly around in 20% women with malignant OC in previous studies [19] similar to our results, in which bilateral ovarian tumor was present in 24.48% of malignant ovarian carcinoma cases. Most of the bilateral tumors were serous adenocarcinoma cases in our study. Studies reported epithelial ovarian cancer as the most common histological type, the present retrospective analysis of 56 cases of benign as well as malignant tumor showed that epithelial ovarian tumors constituted 71.42% (40 cases) of all ovarian cancer cases. Among all OC cases, serous variant of epithelial OC cases was most prevalent with 25% cases. Moreover, mucinous subtype was found in 21.42% women, cystadenoma in 17.85% cases, adenocarcinoma in 10.71% cases and endometrioid in 5.35% cases. Some similar kind of studies suggested that, incidence of serous variant of adenocarcinoma was most common in all epithelial types of carcinoma ovary [20]. Clinically, bioassay for serum CA-125 level is reported as potential and liable tumor marker for diagnosing progression of this disease [21]. In our study we found that nearly 57 % cases of benign tumor showed CA-125 level less than 35 U/l but higher serum level was seen in malignant patients.

CONCLUSION

Ovarian cancer is one of the most common gynecological malignancies affecting in Indian woman. The present study reports the trends in ovarian cancer incidence with demographic factors of the north central region of India. Analysis was done thorough history and clinical examinations by the clinicians to elucidate sociodemographic as well as clinical factors associated with ovarian cancer. Majority of the patients was diagnosed in advanced stage of the disease as the delay in diagnosis was common. Awareness regarding ovarian cancer in general population and also primary care physician may help in early detection and timely treatment of the disease can reduce the mortality and morbidity. There are also changes in socio-demographic, menstrual and reproductive factors, life-style related factors contribute to changes in the incidence of future ovarian cancer in India.

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